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**CASTIEL 2 – Coordination & Support
for National Competence Centres on a European Level Phase 2**

Project Number: 101102047

D5.5

Second report on awareness, impact and outreach

EuroHPC
Joint Undertaking

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List of abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
C2ISS	CASTIEL 2 Information Sharing System
CD	Corporate Design
CoE	Centre of Excellence
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
D	Deliverable
EBDVF	European Big Data Value Forum
GA	Grant Agreement
HPC	High-Performance Computing
ISC	ISC High Performance – Wissenschaftliche Konferenz zu Supercomputing/HPC
JU	Joint Undertaking
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
M	Month
NCC	National Competence Centre
PMT	Project Management Team
SC	The International Conference for High Performance Computing Networking, Storage, and Analysis (Supercomputing)
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprises
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

Executive Summary

The document “D5.5: Second report on awareness, impact and outreach” is the fifth deliverable of CASTIEL 2’s Work Package 5 (WP5): Awareness, Impact and Outreach. This document reports on the communication and dissemination activities from and related to CASTIEL 2 in the second year of the project. It will be further updated and reported on in D5.7 (M36).

WP5 plans and implements communication and dissemination measures that are related to and support the achievement of the CASTIEL 2 project’s objectives, as well as assisting the National Competence Centres (NCCs) of the EuroCC 2 project and EuroHPC JU funded Centres of Excellence (CoEs) in HPC with their communication efforts.

This deliverable 5.5 is divided into two main parts: the first covers the communication and dissemination work, the second presents the support of National Competence Centres for High Performance Computing (NCCs) and the Centres of Excellence (CoEs).

Main achievements in this second year of the project runtime were the ongoing support of communication champions, new events were held (e.g. Bridging Minds) and new communication measures like two Success Story Booklets¹ and the Supercomputing in Europe Podcast² were implemented; all KPIs are well underway.

¹ <https://www.eurocc-access.eu/services/document-library/>

² <https://open.spotify.com/show/4pZ7nfUZTs3tDyfwVFAR8q>

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1 Introduction

The Coordination and Support Action (CSA) CASTIEL 2 leads to cross-European networking activities between National Competence Centres and EuroHPC JU funded Centres of Excellence in HPC-related topics. The other CoEs that were funded in previous funding programmes will be included in collaboration when beneficial to the network. In the following, CoE refers to the CoEs funded by the EuroHPC JU, if not specified otherwise.

CASTIEL 2 focuses on four core areas: Competences, Training, Industry Collaboration as well as Communication and Dissemination.

WP5 in CASTIEL 2 – Awareness, Impact and Outreach – operates on multiple levels. Firstly, this WP communicates the CASTIEL 2 projects’ contents, aims, and results. Secondly, this WP maintains the EuroCC and hpccoe brands (for NCCs and CoEs, respectively). Thirdly, the support of NCCs and CoEs is also in the scope of this WP’s work. The creation and maintenance of the C2ISS (CASTIEL 2 Information Sharing System) and a newly developed CI/CD tool (Continuous Integration, Continuous Deployment) is also part of this work package, but since these topics have their own deliverables (D5.2 and D5.8 and updates thereof), they will not be described here.

The main goals for this work package have also been set in the initial dissemination strategy, as described in D5.1:

- *Continue and increase awareness about the EuroCC and hpccoe brands*
- *Create and promote the Competence and Excellence Network brand*
- *Support the CoEs’ and NCCs’ communication efforts*

Figure 1: EuroCC and hpccoe main logos

The second goal foreseen in the initial strategy was to create an umbrella brand for the EuroCC and hpccoe brands. However, seen that updating and maintaining the hpccoe brand requires more effort than initially estimated and not to overburden the new CoEs with too much branding work, creating and implementing the umbrella brand is on hold for now with a tendency to shift this topic to the next project implementation. This leaves the two main goals:

- *Continue and increase awareness about the EuroCC and hpccoe brands*
- *Support the CoEs and NCCs communication efforts*

This report gives a comprehensive and extensive overview about the work done and the results achieved in these tasks during the project. Section 2 summarises the efforts and results when it comes to dissemination and communication, Section 3 shows how the NCCs and CoEs are supported and Section 4 provides a summary and outlook towards the next project months.

2 Dissemination and Communication

In this Section, the communication about and from the projects in year two are presented and the overall progress is evaluated.

2.1 Goals and Channels

The main goal of this WP's outreach efforts was to further establish the NCCs as first contact point to the "world of HPC" and the CoEs as excellence hubs in specific domains and associated with spearheading algorithm development (the stakeholders chosen in the initial strategy can be found in "D5.1: Initial Dissemination Plan"). One focus of CASTIEL 2 is to extend the knowledge about the brands outside of the HPC ecosystem, e.g., more specific end users and the general public.

The communication channels from CASTIEL 1 were kept (EuroCC ACCESS, X (former Twitter) and LinkedIn). The FocusCoE channels were reactivated and rebranded to the hpccoe brand. The main dissemination channels remain (as in phase one as proven effective), the web channels and events. To see the evaluation of how these channels contributed to the goals, see Table 1; the impact was estimated based on lead generation, brand awareness and reach with a scoring system.

Channel	Impact in Target Group
EuroCC ACCESS ^[1]	Mid
hpccoe.eu ^[2]	Mid
X (Twitter) EuroCC ^[3]	Low
X (Twitter) hpccoe ^[4]	Low
LinkedIn EuroCC ^[5]	High
LinkedIn hpccoe ^[6]	High
Press Releases	Mid
Events	Very High

Table 1: Evaluation of Channels by CASTIEL

The table shows that the X (Twitter) channels have been rated as a low impact. This is because of the development of the platform in the last year. The HPC community is not as present as it used to be, since technical and content quality of the platform declined. This WP monitors current and future alternatives. Mastodon was considered, but, given the low representation of the target group, not implemented. The same assessment was done for Threads. Seeing the recent rise in BlueSky users in our target groups, trial accounts will be coordinated with NCCs and CoEs.

2.1.1 Update on Event Participation

Table 2 shows a summary of events in which CASTIEL 2 participated, a description of how the project was represented and a short evaluation of their effectiveness. It can be seen that towards the end of 2024, there is a shift from active participation as WP5 towards a coordinating role. This is due to the limits in travel budget. As for the future, CASTIEL 2 WP5 will take a more active role in EuroHPC Summit Week and ISC in 2025. For other events, the WP will assist

participating NCCs and CoEs with budget (Booth, Passes) as well as coordination of conference programme, booth plan etc.

Event	Date	Summary	Evaluation
EuroHPC Summit Week 2023	20.03. – 23.03.2023	Participated in Conference Programme	Valuable for establishing the brands within the HPC ecosystem
ISC 2023	22.05. – 24.05.2023	Represented in EuroHPC JU booth	Valuable for establishing the brands within the HPC ecosystem, some industry contact
Supercomputing Day Luxembourg	04.05.2023	Participated in Sessions & presented a high-level view of the CoEs & their codes	Valuable for establishing the brands within the HPC ecosystem
EBDVF 2023	25.10. – 27.10.2023	Participated with a booth, participated in Conference Programme	Valuable for reaching an industrial target group, industry contact
SC 2023	14.11. – 17.11.2023	Represented in HLRS Booth	Valuable for establishing the brands within the international HPC ecosystem
EuroHPC Summit Week 2024	18.03.- 21.03.2024	Participated in Conference Programme	Valuable for establishing the brands within the HPC ecosystem
ISC 2024	12.05.- 16.05.2024	Represented in EuroHPC JU booth with own area	Valuable for establishing the brands within the HPC ecosystem, some industry contact
EBDVF 2024	02.10.- 04.10.2024	Participated in Conference Programme	Valuable for reaching an industrial target group, industry contact
EuroHPC JU User Day 2024	22.10.- 23.10.2024	Participated in an interactive format	Valuable for getting in touch with EuroHPC System users

Table 2: Description and Evaluation of Events Visited

2.1.2 HPC Industry Summit in Berlin

On 18–19 October 2023, together with the FF4EuroHPC project, a joint event towards industry and state representatives was held in Berlin – the HPC Industry Summit.

The conference consisted of two different parts: a project-internal one, exclusively for the Work Package Leaders (WPLs) of the NCCs, and an external one that was open to visitors and that was also livestreamed via YouTube. In the public part, the first day focussed on introductory content such as overviews about HPC+ and its applications and featured Success Stories from the EuroCC project. The second day featured more in-depth topics and premiered Success Stories from the FF4EuroHPC project. See Figure 2 for details of the agenda.

Figure 4: Banner for the Bridging Minds Event

The conference consisted of four different kinds of sessions:

1. Understanding HPC: Topical introductions to HPC, its technical basics and infrastructure in Europe
2. Exploring Use Cases: Existing users from all levels (beginner to professional) presented their use cases from Social Sciences and Humanities
3. Practical Guidance: In interactive sessions, interested possible users were connected to HPC experts, which provided answers and, in some cases, basic consulting
4. Networking Opportunities: Within the interactive sessions, attendees could not only connect to HPC experts, but also to each other

See Figure 5 for details of the agenda.

Day 1 - 09.04.2024		Day 2 - 10.04.2024	
Time	What	Time	What
13:00-13:30	Welcome	08:30-09:00	Welcome
13:30-14:00	What is HPC? What is EuroCC 2?	09:00-10:15	Use Cases (from Social Sciences and Humanities)
14:00-15:00	Use Cases (from Social Sciences and Humanities)	10:15-11:15	Interactive Workshop
15:00-15:15	Coffee Break	11:15-11:30	Wrap Up
15:15-16:30	Interactive Workshop		
16:30-17:00	EuroHPC JU and HPC Systems		

Figure 5: Agenda of the Bridging Minds Event

2.1.4 All Hands Meeting 2024 in Slovakia

On 22-24 April 2024, the first all hands meeting of EuroCC 2 and collaborating projects took place in High Tatras, Slovakia with 115 participants, from NCCs, CoEs and CASTIEL 2. This work package coordinated the conference, which included conceptualising, organising, executing and post-processing. The organisation and execution were done in tight collaboration with the NCC Slovakia team.

The conference was aimed at fostering collaboration and strategic discussions within the projects. Main topics were debriefings about the reviews, identification of synergies and identification of strategic working points.

Time	Main Room (160)	Hunting Lounge (80)	Coffee Lounge (30)	Time	Main Room (160) Track 1	Hunting Lounge (80) Track 2	Coffee Lounge (30) Private Track
09:00 - 09:30	Welcome NATALIE LEWANDOWSKI			09:00 - 09:30	Welcome NATALIE LEWANDOWSKI		
09:30 - 10:45	Review Debrief NATALIE LEWANDOWSKI			09:30 - 10:45	Funding Information Session: Workshops with CASTIEL 2 Budget JISIKA YONO, NATALIE LEWANDOWSKI		Central European Working Group
10:45 - 11:00	Coffee Break			10:45 - 11:00	Coffee Break		
11:00 - 12:00	Identification of Synergies between NCCs & CoE NATALIE LEWANDOWSKI			11:00 - 12:00	Work Package Leader Meeting NATALIE LEWANDOWSKI	CoEs - impact generation & future plans MIRIAM KOCH	Service Catalogue Demonstrator NCC POLAND
12:00 - 13:30	Lunch			12:00 - 13:30	Lunch		
13:30 - 15:00	Identification of Synergies between NCCs & CoE NATALIE LEWANDOWSKI			13:30 - 15:00	KPI Taskforce JISIKA YONO	Thematic Clusters - Industry Approach MARIE-FRANCOISE GERARD	
15:00 - 15:30	Coffee Break			15:00 - 15:30	Coffee Break		
15:30 - 17:00	Discussion: CASTIEL 2 as a Hub - Ideas & Improvements JISIKA YONO			16:00 - 17:00	Excursion around the lake		
From 19:00	Social Event						

Time	Main Room (160)	Hunting Lounge (80)	Coffee Lounge (30)
09:00 - 09:30	Welcome		
09:30 - 10:45	Discussion: Perspectives for the NCC-CoE Network NATALIE LEWANDOWSKI		
10:45 - 11:00	Coffee Break		
11:00 - 12:00	Cross-Cutting Technical Items LAURA MORSELLI	Training Baseline ALINE MELINETTE	
12:00 - 13:30	Lunch		
13:30 - 15:00	EuroCC improved poster BENOÎT DOMPIERRE	C5 Meeting (CASTIEL INTERNAL)	
15:00 - 15:30	Coffee Break		
15:30 - 17:00	Open Discussion Forum (All three rooms available)		

Figure 6: Agenda of All Hands Meeting in Slovakia

2.2 Content Generation from the NCCs/CoEs and Reach Multiplication

In phase two of the project, the NCCs and CoEs already have a great output of content themselves, so the focus shifted more from active content generation to reach multiplication. For that, the NCCs and CoEs have access to content plans for the social media channels (they can provide content and WP5 posts the content to the EuroCC/hpccoe channels) as well as their own content areas on the respective websites (editable themselves in case of EuroCC ACCESS, editable through WP5 upon request in case of hpccoe.eu). Through promoting these channels further, the reach benefit for the Centres grows. Furthermore, an increasing amount of cross-

promoting can be seen, where NCCs and CoEs share each other's content, thus increasing reach again.

2.3 Update on EuroCC Brand

The EuroCC brand continues to be well received by the NCCs. While the main project logo was updated in phase two, the NCC logos remain the same to ensure brand continuity. In the first phase, there was a light and a dark version of the Corporate Design (CD). In phase two, only the light version will be continued. The EuroCC brand (See "D5.1: Initial Communication and Dissemination Plan") is overall well accepted and implemented by the NCCs, with varying degrees of adherence to the CD guidelines.

2.4 Update on hpccoe Brand

The hpccoe brand was reactivated by re-working and updating the hpccoe website as well as taking ownership of the FocusCoE channels which have been rebranded to the hpccoe brand.

2.5 Update on KPIs

For the KPIs set in the GA, the final status is given here in form of a table (see Table 3) including comments, if necessary. All KPIs are well underway.

Tool	KPI	Target total (M1-M36)	Stretch target at M24	Current Status
Publications	Press Releases	2	1	1
	Success Story Booklets	3	1	2
Events	CASTIEL/Network of NCC/CoEs presentations at conferences/events	20	10	9
	Significant presence at events (e.g. booths)	7	3	7
	Number of own events (public)	3	1	2
Social Media	Number of X/Twitter postings, Followers	2-3 posts a week, 300 followers p.a. (for all social media channels)	2-3 posts a week, 300 followers p.a. (for all social media)	Daily Postings, >300 new followers *

			channels)	
	Number of LinkedIn Postings, Followers	Weekly Postings, 250 Followers p.a. (for all social media channels)	weekly postings, 250 followers p.a. (for all social media channels)	Weekly Postings, >650 new followers
Reference in external media channels (Online & Offline)	Press Clippings	40	20	143
Websites	Number of visits	15,000 unique p.a.	15.000	68,657

Table 3: KPIs and Update

* to note: Since the usage of X/Twitter has massively declined/changed in the last years, this KPI might not be achievable.

3 Support of NCCs and CoEs

Another core task of WP5 is to support the communication teams in the NCCs and CoEs through a series of mechanisms. These mechanisms are described in section 3.3. Additionally, an update on the NCCs' communication efforts is given to create a comprehensive picture.

3.1 Summary of CoEs' Efforts

This WP collected communication reporting files regularly, including all relevant KPIs. In detail, these are reported in the Funding and Tenders portal for the respective CoE project. A summary can be found in Table 4.

KPI	# achieved by CoEs in total
Publications	81
Events organised	87
Events attended	270
Press Clippings	55
Press Releases	12
Twitter Followers	9766

LinkedIn Followers	10965
Unique Visitors on Webpages	298462

Table 4: KPIs of CoEs - Summarised

3.2 Summary of NCCs Efforts

This WP collected communication reporting files regularly, including all relevant KPIs. In detail, these are reported in the Funding and Tenders portal for the EuroCC2 project. A summary can be found in Table 5:

KPI	# achieved by NCCs in total
Publications	42
Events organised	369
Events attended	829
Press Clippings	88
Press Releases	47
Social Media Followers	30383
Unique Visitors on Webpages	508029

Table 5: KPIs of NCCs - Summarised

3.3 General Support and Coffee Breaks

In general, Communication Champions can always approach the WP with their request for assistance. In the first year of the project, this was mostly due to staff change in the existing or new staff in the new Centres, who were then on-boarded individually by members of this WP. WP5 attended the two “NCCs-CoEs online meetings” organised by CASTIEL2-WP2 (to fully include the CoEs to CASTIEL 2 activities. The breakout room dedicated to WP5 during the meeting was an important chance to get to know and on-board the CoEs.

Furthermore, the concept of a communication coffee break was successfully launched. These monthly, topic-centred 45-minute sessions allow an informal exchange of experiences between the NCCs’ and CoEs’ Communication Champions. The format was received well with an average attendance between 20 and 25 persons and already resulted in further collaborations among the teams.

Finally, the concept of the catch-up sessions from phase one (See “CASTIEL D5.5: Final report on Communication and Dissemination of and by CASTIEL”) was modified and re-applied to the champions group. Instead of small group sessions, it was held in one singular session at the beginning of year one. During this session, the communication champions can give feedback and bundle requests for WP5.

3.3.1 Communication Champions Meeting in Brussels

As a satellite event to the EuroHPC JU Summit Week 2024, a day long workshop was held in Brussels, which 31 communication champions attended. The event gave opportunity to exchange with and learn from the other communication specialists in the ecosystem.

Timeslot	Topic
09:00-10:30	Workshops 09:00-09:45: Video Editing (Apostolos) 09:45-10:30: Canva (Artemis)
10:30-10:45	Coffee Break
10:45-12:00	Organisational Slot Guntram/Sophia: CoE involvement: Brand, Pain Points, Feedbacks and ideas Miriam: NCCs : Correct Funding Disclaimers Minitalk & Eligibility of Dissemination Costs - Q&A
12:00-13:00	Lunch
13:00-14:00	Brainstorming EuroCC / hpccoe 20 mins: EuroCC/ hpccoe Brand, Formats, Content Types 20 mins: Topic/Formats for CoEs (e.g. Success Story/Impact Booklet?) Discussion on CoE Specific Target Audiences 10 mins: Collaboration 10 mins: Joint Events
14:00-14:15	Coffee Break
14:15-15:45	Workshops 14:15-15:00: WordPress (Miriam) 15:00-15:45: The HPC in Europe Podcast (Apostolos, Miriam)
15:45-16:00	Coffee Break
16:00-17:00	Exchange Visibility of Events in the network Maximise the potential of LinkedIn

Figure 7: Agenda of Communication Meeting in Brussels

3.4 Distributed Materials

In phase one, a plethora of material was produced and distributed to the NCCs (e.g., print templates, social media material etc.). These materials were updated (e.g., with new funding disclaimers and logos, it was also decided which material should also be available to the CoEs, since they have different communication needs and brands. For example, templates produced for the NCCs will not be of use for the CoEs, since they have their own corporate design and do not use the EuroCC brand. Material like the image pool filled with AI generated, royalty free imagery, or a list of all social media channels, was made accessible to all.

3.4.1 NCC Booklets

To showcase Use Cases and Success Stories from the NCCs, Work Package 4 sourced and curated a number of articles from the NCCs, targeted towards industry. WP5 turned these articles into booklets ^{[7],[8]} and printed them as well as distributed them on events and to stakeholders. The reception was very positive of all recipients. A similar CoE booklet is in the works together with WP4.

Figure 8: Covers of Success Story Booklets

3.4.2 Supercomputing in Europe Podcast

NCC Sweden led the initiative to launch a common podcast^[9] among all NCCs and CoEs. For this, WP5 and NCC Sweden produced Guidelines and Workshops to help all interested communication champions to contribute. The podcast is now launched with five initial episodes; analytics will be provided in the next update. The podcast is conceptualised in a very heterogeneous way, in terms of content, runtime, moderators and format of the interview. This is to reflect the diverse HPC landscape in Europe and enable interesting topics to surface.

Figure 9: Cover of Supercomputing in Europe Podcast

3.5 Specific CoE Support

During year two, many of the activities for year one continued. Social media changes (Twitter/X and LinkedIn) were regularly fed, using a free content schedule with CoEs providing posts of timely content. In late 2024, some CoEs raised their growing concerns against relying on X/Twitter as a prime channel, as increasingly anti-scientific and hostile attitudes could be

observed on that platform and an exodus of scientists to Bluesky was underway. It was thus decided to establish social media channels on Bluesky as well and observe the developments³.

As an additional channel, a regular newsletter featuring highlights and key events from the CoEs was agreed and implemented after the summer break, using LinkedIn as platform which has proven to work very well for some CoEs^[10].

The website hpccoe.eu was maintained: Material was collected from the CoEs to update the website which was also brought up-to-date, though no major updates were published there, anticipating the go-live of C2ISS.

Support for promoting the webinar series “Code of the Month” organised jointly by WP4 and WP2 continued (see D4.1 and D2.1 for details), reaching its 12th instalment in December 2024. Past episodes are listed on the EuroCC website^[11].

WP5 supported WP4 in the collection and revision of the first success stories from the CoEs.

Regular meetings of the CoE Communication Champions working group continued roughly once per quarter, which featured exchange on experience and approaches for dissemination targets of interest, like outreach to specific groups like younger people and groups underrepresented in HPC, in particular women. From that working group, a number of CoEs joined forces to organise two workshops on the work of CoEs at HiPEAC 2025^[12]. The speaker panels of these workshops promote inclusivity and put into focus the contributions of women, marginalized groups and young career researchers in HPC, with some contribution planned from CASTIEL2. One of the topics discussed in the working group revolved around the difficulties to extract meaningful and interesting success stories from the very technical work of the CoEs. Devising strategies to approach and receive useful feedback from both code users and developers were identified as beneficial work areas, and podcasts as a potentially good way to convey more technical or work-in-progress information in a lively and appealing way. CoEs are already contributing to the “HPC in Europe podcast” series (see above). To better address the very specific needs of communication of the CoE, it is planned to follow up on these topics with dedicated workshops to share related best practices and strategies.

During the first year, the working group of the CoE Communication Champions was set up, as an additional forum to the general coffee break meetings to discuss and develop specific dissemination aspects of interest to the CoEs in particular. Meetings are anticipated in regular intervals every few months. One of the first decisions was to set up a social media content plan that serves initially Twitter and LinkedIn which are the most used channels of the CoEs. Starting after the summer break, the still existing channels from FocusCoE were revived as @HPCCoE (Twitter) and @HPC CoE (LinkedIn) and each week one of the new CoEs was presented. After these 10 weeks, a free content schedule is anticipated where CoEs fill in their upcoming events and news.

One of the areas of interest for many CoEs was identified as outreach to young people, students and young professionals. This topic will be followed up in the next year.

³ <https://bsky.app/profile/eurocc.bsky.social> and respective CoE Bluesky pages

4 Conclusion and Outlook on CASTIEL 2

The work done by WP 5 was based on the initial strategy for communication and dissemination presented in D5.1 and first reported on in D5.3. This strategy has been adapted in some minor aspects (e.g., postponing the umbrella brand), but mainly followed through. The significant communication KPIs from the NCCs and CoEs show a broad reach of the respective brands.

Overall, this WP assesses itself in a good progress when it comes to the reported tasks. The KPIs are well underway and the communication channels, both external and internal, are running well. This deliverable is going to be updated in “D5.7: Final report on awareness, impact and outreach”.

5 References

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